

Kammern-Grubgraben revisited - First results from renewed investigations at a well-known LGM site in East Austria

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Abstract

Kammern-Grubgraben is among the few stratified Upper Palaeolithic sites in Central Europe dating to the Last Glacial Maximum which provided not only substantial amounts of archaeological materials but also extensive preserved occupational structures. Although the site has been known since the last quarter of the 19th century, systematic excavations didn't start until the 1980's. These were carried out subsequently by two different teams providing partly incongruent observations and interpretations. Renewed field investigations commenced in 2015 and aim at reassessing stratigraphy and chronology, settlement structures and occupational sequence, as well as mobility and economy. First results provide a robust multi-method chrono-stratigraphic bracket for occupation between Greenland Stadials GS-3 and GS-2.1. Artefact technology and typology point at supra-regional contacts to both the west and east on a more general scale while a high degree of mobility is specifically demonstrated for the hunter-gatherer groups occupying the site by displaying procurement patterns for various raw materials targeting not only local, but also regional and far-distance sources. Furthermore, the new investigations have been able to almost double the previously established site extent, and targeted excavations show that the diversity and complexity of stone constructions considerably exceeds what has previously been observed.

Keywords

Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), lithic technology, raw material procurement, ¹⁴C/OSL chronology, Upper Paleolithic stone constructions, fossils as adornments

1. Introduction

Kammern-Grubgraben is one of the few stratified sites in the Middle Danube Region dating to the timeframe of the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) *sensu stricto*, i.e. the timespan in the last glacial cycle with maximised global ice volume. Maximal glaciation, however, varied with geographic position and the ages given depend upon archive, proxy and method of age determination (e.g. Mix et al., 2001: 23-19/24-18 ka cal BP; Peltier and Fairbanks, 2006: 26-21 ka; Clark et al., 2009: 26.5-20/19 ka; Hughes and Gibbard, 2015: 27,540-23,340 b2k). The

comparably sparse archaeological record for the LGM in Central Europe has been connected to a sharp decrease or even absence of human populations due to low temperatures and extreme aridity (e.g. Terberger and Street, 2002; Verpoorte, 2004; Terberger, 2013; Maier et al. 2016). Major environmental changes are also reflected by the faunal record, which documents decline of woolly mammoth in the second half of Greenland Stadial GS-3, followed by its disappearance and eventual reappearance (Nadachowski et al., 2018), and migration of saiga antelope from the east (Nadachowski et al., 2016). On the other hand, valleys in low mountain ranges in the southern part of Central Europe may have provided protection from extremely cold arctic winds, allowing for higher biotope diversity and increased biomass productivity in refuge areas in and adjacent to the Moravian-Bohemian highlands and the Carpathian forelands in Slovakia and Hungary (Nerudová and Neruda, 2015, and references therein). A similar scenario may also be considered for the valley of the Kamp river, a tributary to the Danube, and adjacent areas in Austria where LGM sites are clustered in a comparable geomorphic setting (Fig. 1a, 2). This is also pointed at by conclusions drawn from previously conducted malacological studies at Kammern-Grubgraben (Frank and Rabeder, 1996).

Kammern-Grubgraben, in publications often referred to as ‘Grubgraben’ or ‘Grubgraben bei Kammern’, is located in the southeast extension of the Moravian-Bohemian highland, in Austria referred to as Waldviertel. The site (elevation ca. 265 m) occupies a gentle loess-covered slope at the foot of the Heiligenstein hill (360 m) which merges into what today appears as a narrow terrace between this and the Geißberg hill (336 m) to the east (Fig. 1b), a result of historic landscape modification for wine cultivation. In the past, it was rather an asymmetrical trough-shaped valley with a gentler slope to the Heiligenstein, where the loess cover is thicker, and a steeper ascent to the Geißberg, at the foot of which the main drainage runs southwest to the Kamp river. A secondary drainage cuts into the valley from the north, and most probably marks the west limit of the site. Both drainages follow tectonic joints. Kammern-Grubgraben is exposed to the south towards the valley of the Kamp river (ca. 200 m) and the Danube plain, but also provides access to the Moravian plateau in the northwest. The site was thus protected from predominant westerly and northwesterly winds (e.g. Zeeden et al., 2015 for preferred wind directions in MIS3/2). The occupations represented by the main archaeological sequence at Kammern-Grubgraben are dated to ca. 23-22 ka cal BP and a connection to the brief phases of climatic improvement during Greenland Interstadials GI-2.2 and GI-2.1 (Fig. 2) has been hypothesised based on both radiocarbon chronology and stratigraphic observations (Haesaerts, 1990; Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016). Based on

thermoluminescence dates, Zöller (2001) placed the sequence into the Upper Pleniglacial, prior to the LGM.

Today, the site is cut by a hollow way that runs along the foot of the Heiligenstein (Fig. 3). This is the location where Palaeolithic finds were noticed and first reported on in 1890 (Spöttl, 1890; Obermaier, 1908). Since then, a range of both official and unauthorised collections and soundings have been carried out. Investigations with systematic excavations, however, commenced but in 1985 and targeted the area east of the hollow way. They were conducted by A. Montet-White/F. Brandtner from 1985-1990 and by F. Brandtner/B. Klíma in 1993 and 1994 (Brandtner, 1990; 1996; Montet-White, 1988; 1990). The field investigations exposed a sequence of up to five superimposed archaeological layers (AL): AL 1, the latest occupation with significantly fewer and more dispersed structures and finds; AL 2-4 representing the main occupation phase with extensive stone slab features and rich finds inventories; and AL 5 with only few scattered finds exposed but in the northeast of the excavated area. The archaeological material includes not only a variable lithic industry with typo-technologically distinct artefacts, but also a rich organic industry with numerous eyed needles, ivory points, spatulas, a bâton percé, a spear thrower, as well as a flute made of a reindeer bone (Einwögerer and Käfer, 1998; Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2008; 2016). Based on the combination of chronological position and typological variability of the industry, Montet-White (1990) placed the site into a wider Epigravettian context while the Brandtner (1996) considered autochthonous techno-cultural development, and Terberger (2003) proposed defining Kammern-Grubgraben as reference for a group of sites in Central Europe with similar attributes. This proposal, together with the term 'Grubgrabian', however, did not find wider acceptance (e.g. Svoboda and Novák, 2004).

In 2013, the Quaternary Archaeology research group of the Institute for Oriental and European Archaeology of the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OREA) initialised an inventory project in cooperation with the Institutes of Prehistoric Archaeology of the University of Cologne (J. Richter) and the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (A. Maier). Hereby, the find material was sorted and inventoried by students trained in Palaeolithic Archaeology. 23,000 inventory numbers were assigned in the course of this project which was funded by the State of Lower Austria (Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016). Exposure of stone features on the lower terrace southeast of the known site in the course of construction works in 2015 were the starting point for a new phase of field investigations conducted by OREA's Quaternary Archaeology research group (Einwögerer, 2017).

2. Materials and methods

Since fieldwork is still ongoing, we can only, at this stage of research, present materials, methodologies, and results which are both preliminary and partial. Hereby, we focus on site layout, stratigraphy, as well as radiocarbon and luminescence chronology. Investigation of the material culture so far concentrated mainly on chipped stone artefacts, personal adornments, and architectural elements, i.e. stone blocks and slabs. Faunal remains, in contrast, have not yet been studied in detail. At present, we can thus but confirm the assessments of previous work, and state that the new assemblage is also vastly dominated by mid-sized ungulates, primarily reindeer and horse, which are represented by all body parts suggesting transport of entire carcasses to the site (Logan, 1990; 2000). The mammoth/rhino size category is absent (in previous excavation's inventory only represented by mammoth ivory), and small mammals are rare.

2.1 Recent excavations 2015-2019

As mentioned above, recent field investigations commenced in 2015. First focus was the terrace southwest of the area of previous investigations where a well-pronounced find layer was hit by a bulldozer while carrying out earthworks as preparation for a new agricultural road. In consequence, the work was stopped and the affected area underwent archaeological investigations. This was conducted in form of two test trenches (C12-13, Z-D/2-3), both of which hit substantial Upper Palaeolithic deposits (Fig. 3). While trench C12-13 exposed a rich find scatter with mainly chipped stone artefacts and poorly preserved faunal remains, trench Z-D/2-3 also yielded a structural feature in form of a surface created with several dozen stone slabs, and thus a finding very similar to the stone features documented by the previous excavations (Einwögerer, 2017). Surprising, however, was the distance to the area of previous investigations, 40 m to the northeast. In addition, previous fieldwork documented decreased settlement intensity and fading out of the main archaeological sequence AL 2-4 with its stone features to the southwest (e.g. Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016). The new discovery therefore triggered the question of how it relates stratigraphically and chronologically to the previous excavation results. As bulldozing had already removed the sediments on the lower terrace atop the exposed archaeological layer, trench Z-D/2-3 was extended one metre into the upper terrace (square E3) in order to expose the sedimentary context above and below, resulting in a > 4 m profile. Square E3 showed that the stone feature layer fades out rapidly to the northwest, and that there is a faint layer with few dispersed finds ca. 0.3 m atop. We named

the layers archaeological horizon (AH) 102 and AH 101 resp. and hypothesised that the upper, faint layer (AH 101) corresponds to AL 1, and the horizon with denser find scatter and the stone feature (AH 102) to sequence AL 2-4. This obviously required testing. Since excavation on the lower terrace was authorised for archaeological assessment regarding the planned construction of the agricultural road only, we hence focussed our investigations on the upper terrace. Here, we first localised and then extended the northeast corner of the main area of previous excavations to the northeast in order to investigate an area where sequence AL 2-4 was reportedly very well developed (trench 1), tested the previous excavations' limits (which, unfortunately, do not correspond to the published plans) by coring and excavation of trench 2, re-excavated trench TP86 to get quick access to a profile with a long sediment sequence, and started excavating trench 3 from northeast to southwest in order to determine the stratigraphic relationship between the findings on the upper and lower terraces. On the upper terrace, we denominated the archaeological horizons AH 1 (upper layer) and AH 2 (main sequence). The latter was divided into several subunits, the lowermost of which in trench 1 could correspond to AL 4 as described by the previous excavators (Brandtner, 1996; Montet-White, 1990).

2.2 Typo-technological analyses of lithic artefacts

For the technological and typological analyses of the chipped lithic artefacts, an inventory of 1160 blanks and 153 cores (total: 1313) of the excavation campaigns 2015-2018 have been studied. Data recording followed the established system developed by Auffermann et al. (1990) which was augmented by features regarding differentiation between different percussion instruments (Maier, 2015).

The inventory of the new excavations belongs to four stratigraphic assemblages: AH 1, AH 101, AH 2, and AH 102 (see above). There are pronounced differences regarding artefact abundances. AH 101 is represented by 2 artefacts only, and AH 102 by 162 artefacts. AH 1 yielded 40 lithics, while AH 2 provided 1098 pieces. 11 specimens originate from disturbed contexts and can therefore not be connected to a specific layer. We assumed that AH 1 and AH 101 correspond to AL 1, and AH 2 and AH 102 to AL 2-3(4) of the previous excavations, and tested this hypothesis by means of typo-technological analyses. The lowermost subdivision of AH 2 in trench 1 which could potentially correspond to previous excavations' AL 4 was only assessed in 2019; its lithic collection has therefore not yet been studied.

2.3 Lithic raw material

For the present study, AH 1 and AH 101, as well as AH 2 and AH 102 were summarily investigated. Accordingly, 38 lithic artefacts were examined from AH 1/101, and 1213 from AH 2/102. These represent specimens that belong to the chipped stone industry, but include only pieces for which the raw materials were determinable.

A two-stage analytical procedure was applied for raw material and preliminary provenance studies. In the first stage, visually homogeneous groups were separated within the assemblages. Subsequently, these groups were tested for their consistency using a Zeiss SteREO Discovery V20 stereomicroscope on unpolished rock surfaces, typically under a 20-150 times magnification and water immersion. Stereomicroscopy aims at the identification of characteristics such as the microstructure, i.e. size, shape and spatial arrangement of the rock-building components, as well as of particular inclusions. In the case of chert, the investigation focusses primarily on the detection and identification of microfossil remains. Non-fossil inclusions, however, are also recorded and may be representative of specific source environments (Affolter, 2002; Brandl, 2014; Brooks, 1989; Přichystal, 1984). Based on this approach and using the extensive comparative raw material collection housed at the OREA Raw Material Lab, it was possible, in most cases, to establish the source region of the lithic artefacts.

2.4 Adornments

In prehistory, adornments are generally understood to be objects that have no function as tools and can be attached (Hahn, 1992). The technical focus of this definition aims at avoiding transfer of our current understanding of jewellery into a Palaeolithic context. However, this definition also implies that Palaeolithic reality can only be reproduced to a limited extent covering but a part of the former aesthetic and symbolic behaviour (Floss, 2003; Ladier and Welté, 1994). We therefore include unmodified objects such as fossil shark teeth in the adornment inventory, which may have been collected for their aesthetic quality only. The same applies for unperforated canines and fossil mollusc shells considering these may have represented blanks for pendants.

Kammern-Grubgraben revealed a rich and varied adornment inventory. So far, however, this inventory has only been partially published (Montet-White, 1990; Brandtner, 1990; 1996). In an (ongoing) review of the find material from the previous excavations, nearly 600 fossil molluscs were recorded thus far, together with 16 tooth pendants and a few perforated stone objects (Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016). Adornments have been recorded for all layers, with the exception of AL 5, and dentalia dominate throughout the sequence.

The new field investigations 2015-2019 provided 39 objects classified as adornments. AH 1 provided three objects; two were recovered from AH 102, and 34 from AH 2. With the exception of one stone pendant (AH 2), all are fossils. Palaeontological determination and classification of the fossils was performed at the Natural History Museum Vienna.

2.5 Stratigraphy and formation of archaeological layers

The stratigraphic observations documented in course of previous fieldwork at Kammern-Grubgraben are not congruent. The stratigraphic frame of the sediment sequence was established by Haesaerts (1990), and the documented archaeological stratigraphy of the first excavation phase conducted by A. Montet-White was comprehensively intercalated into this frame (Montet-White, 1988, 1990). Brandtner (1996), however, did not agree with all previous assessments, in particular with the connection of humic horizons (HH 1 and HH 2) to sequence AL 2-4. He denominated the archaeological layers 'Kulturschicht' (KS) and parallelised these with the AL used by A. Montet-White. However, in the area where F. Brandtner conducted the excavations, KS3 represents the main unit with built stone features, in contrast to A. Montet-White's excavations, where these structures are connected to AL 2, resp. AL 2a and 2b (Haesaerts, 1990; Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016). Both main excavators, however, considered the archaeological sequence AL 1-5 resp. KS 1-5 as direct result of five successive occupations whereas natural formation processes (Schiffer, 1983) are granted a minor role only. The incongruencies regarding stratigraphic observations in the crucial part of the archaeological sequence demanded establishing an independent stratigraphic framework for the new investigations.

2.6 Radiocarbon chronology

Since charcoal is practically absent from the site of Kammern-Grubgraben (Haesaerts et al., 2016), all radiocarbon ages produced both on the previous excavations' material and on samples recovered during new fieldwork were measured on animal bones and teeth (exclusively reindeer and horse when determinable). A total of 20 radiocarbon dates were produced on faunal remains of the previous excavations by four different laboratories (Arizona, Louvaine-la-Neuve, Groningen, Mannheim). In the latest discussion of the radiocarbon chronology published prior to recent fieldwork, Haesaerts et al. (2016) reject all ages appearing too late for the according archaeological layer. This includes all dates produced by the laboratories in Arizona and Louvaine-la-Neuve, as well as one date from Groningen. Result is a radiocarbon chronology which is coherent to the archaeological

sequence. The approach of our new investigations attempts avoiding a priori assertions. In a first step, we aimed at obtaining ages for the new area on the lower terrace (AH 102), recovering a suitable sample for the upper layer (AH 1) as well as for AH 2 in trenches 1 and TP86. Hitherto, five samples recovered in the course of the new excavations have been selected and dated at the Curt-Engelhorn-Zentrum Archäometrie in Mannheim (Germany). Calibration of all radiocarbon ages was carried out with the IntCal13 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2014) using the OxCal 4.3 web tool - web interface build number: 122; last updated: 12/3/2020; accessed 25/3/2020 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009).

2.7 Luminescence chronology

A series of thermoluminescence (TL) dates have already been produced in the scope of previous investigations. Zöller (2001) reports four TL ages (GRUB1: 14 ± 1.5 ka for the latest glacial loess situated above the archaeological sequence; GRUB2: 19.9 ± 1.7 ka for a sample taken beneath AL/KS 2; GRUB3: 21.3 ± 2.2 ka under AL/KS 4; GRUB4: 22 ± 2.1 ka for a sample taken from AL/KS 5; BOH2: 47.3 ± 7.3 ka from a drilling at 2 m depth) which he found to be in agreement with the radiocarbon ages reported by Haesaerts (1990). The samples were recovered in 1993 prior to F. Brandtner's excavations, and there are a few peculiarities regarding the sampling locations. The sample providing the latest date was collected from a hollow way profile 200 m downhill from the site. Although the assessment that the sediment represents fill of a palaeochannel can be confirmed, the profile published for its contextualisation (Zöller, 2001) in fact represents trench TP85 (Haesaerts, 1990; see Fig. 3 for location) which is definitely incorrect. Unfortunately, sample BOH2 cannot be placed horizontally or vertically. Samples GRUB2 to GRUB4 were taken from an undocumented position in the hollow way. Reportedly, AL/KS 1 and AL/KS 5 did not occur here implying that the contextualising profile TR85 doesn't represent the sampling location's stratigraphy. Our own observations in trench TP86, which is in close proximity to the hollow way, confirm the presence of a faintly expressed AH 1 and a non-separable main sequence AH 2 showing a high degree of post-occupational displacement (3.4). The stratigraphy exposed in the hollow way today displays an even higher degree of displacement and suggests absence of in situ contexts. We therefore consider the stratigraphic placement of samples GRUB2-4 as highly insecure. This is further enhanced by the observation of considerable sediment input from the slope to the Heiligenstein. The age underestimation connected to slope processes discussed by Zöller (2001) for Willendorf, may therefore also be assumed for the Kammern-Grubgraben samples.

This recommended undertaking a new luminescence approach with better stratigraphic control. With start of the new excavation campaigns, a first series of ten OSL samples were recovered in 2015; two samples from beneath AL 2-4, resp. AH 2 at the boundary of the previously excavated area to trench 1, and eight samples from the long sequence exposed in square E3 (Fig. 4). All samples were recovered in pairs, i.e. from two more or less adjacently placed cylinders in five positions. Sample preparation was carried out in the Laboratory of Luminescence Dating and Dosimetry in Cluj-Napoca (Romania). Luminescence analyses were conducted in Cluj-Napoca and, during one stage of research, at the Nordic Laboratory for Luminescence Dating in Roskilde (Denmark).

The ten samples were prepared in dimmed red light conditions, where the end material from the tubes was removed and used to determine water contents and dose rates while the core material was further processed (protocol from previous published studies e.g. Constantin et al., 2012) in order to obtain the coarse (63-90 μm) quartz. Radionuclide (U-238/Ra-226, Th-232, K-40) specific activities were measured by high-resolution gamma spectrometry and the conversion factors of Adamiec and Aitken (1998) were used for deriving the dose rates. Luminescence measurements were performed using two automated Risø TL/OSL-DA-20 readers equipped with blue and infrared light diodes emitting at 470 ± 30 nm and 875 ± 80 nm, respectively. The emitted luminescence signals were detected by EMI 9235QA photomultiplier tube (Thomsen et al., 2008). Irradiation of the samples was completed using the incorporated $^{90}\text{Sr} - ^{90}\text{Y}$ beta source, calibrated using gamma irradiated calibration quartz (Hansen et al., 2015). The dose rates of 0.0389 Gy/s and 0.1439 Gy/s were derived for the coarse (63-90 μm) quartz grains deposited on stainless steel disks.

3. Results

At this stage of research, we can but present first results, since field investigations at Kammern-Grubgraben are ongoing and only a part of the recovered material has hitherto been studied. Nevertheless, however, the new excavations already provide a range of novel insights. A very important result is the recently established considerably increased site extent which nearly doubled compared to assessments of the previous excavators (Fig. 3). This is highly relevant not only for conservation matters (Einwögerer, 2017) but also for general considerations and interpretations regarding site function, economy, or span and frequency of occupation(s). When referring to the archaeological unit denominations used in the previous excavations we will use 'AL' to refer to both AL and KS, unless otherwise stated. We

commence with the result of the typo-technological analyses as it provided the highest resolution for testing coherence among the archaeological units.

3.1 Technology and typology of the chipped stone inventory

We already mentioned that the lower layers AH 2 and AH 102 yielded substantially higher numbers of lithic artefacts than the upper layers AH 1 and AH 101 (Table 1). This finding is consistent with observations of the previous excavations (Montet-White, 1990; Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016), where the clearly distinguishable AL 1 yielded only 7 % of the entire lithic inventory, whereas the lower layers, which are less well separated from one another, comprise about 70 % of all lithic artefacts when including multi-layer assemblages AL 2-3 and AL 2-4 (AL 2: ca. 5%, AL 3 ca. 54%; AL 4: ca. 7%). However, it has to be noted that almost one fourth of the lithic inventory recovered during previous fieldwork cannot be attributed to a specific archaeological unit.

With regard to core technology, there are no discernable differences between the assemblages of the previous (Montet-White, 1990; Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016) and the new excavations. A characteristic feature of the entire Kammern-Grubgraben inventory is the large variety of technological concepts applied for the production of flakes, blades, and bladelets (Table 2). Among the cores, there are primary cores on raw volumes and cores-on-flakes. Here, the term core-on-flake comprises any blank, both flakes and blades, with subsequent production of flakes, blades or bladelets. The production of the blanks used for cores-on-flakes is not attested on site and was probably carried out elsewhere (Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016). Primary cores comprise both flake and blade cores. Flake cores often show the opportunistic use of suitable striking angles, and, when exhausted, often display multiple striking and reduction faces. Blade cores are usually more standardised and exhibit regular Upper Palaeolithic features (e.g. crested blades, core tablets, etc.). Cores-on-flakes were directed towards the production of bladelets and, to a lesser degree, blades and flakes. Bladelet production follows three directions, namely along the distal edge, the lateral edges, or the (usually distal) volume of the blanks (Fig. 5).

For bladelet production along the lateral edges of blanks, both flakes and blades are used (Fig. 5a). The edges can be retouched or left unmodified. In some cases, small striking platforms are prepared. The production sequence is usually limited to 1-3 blades/bladelets, and discarded cores show identical morphologies to burins. Bladelets are also produced from the distal edges (both retouched and unmodified) of flakes and blades, with or without preparation of a striking platform (Fig. 5b). The length of the bladelets is limited by the width

of the blank, and the production sequence is usually short. In this case, the discarded cores resemble transversal burins.

A comparison of the median dimensions of cores for lateral and distal removal of blades/bladelets (Table 2) between AH 1 (n=3), AH 2 (n=81), and AH 102 (n=6) shows that they are longer and wider, but less thick in AH 2 (28.9/11.6/16.5 mm) and AH 102 (28.3/12.7/12.9 mm), than in AH 1 (20.0/7.9/19.0 mm). While this is in agreement with observations regarding dimensions of the corresponding blanks in AH 2 and AH 102, it is at odds with observations for AH 1 (Fig. 5; Table 3). In some cases, the distal end was retouched and the retouch used as a crest for the first bladelet. Occasionally, bladelet production shifted subsequently onto the ventral surface of the blank (Fig. 5c). The discarded cores then resemble *pièces d'Orville/de Bertonne* (Chehmana, 2011). Sometimes, bladelet production occurred along the ridges of the dorsal negatives (Fig. 5d). In their general morphology, the discarded cores resemble so-called 'Kostenki knives' or 'La Marche cores'.

One method of flake production from cores-on-flake uses thick and longer blanks with triangular cross section as cores (Fig. 5e). Using the ventral face as striking platform, a series of short, overlapping or non-overlapping flakes is produced. These flakes usually show a roundish outline and end in hinges, making them suitable for the production of *raclettes* or *raclette-like* artefacts (Fig. 6g-i). The resulting negatives are similar to the trimming negatives along the edges of the cores with an exploitation of the distal volume. These cores-on-flake are made on rather thick and elongated blanks. Usually, these cores show lateral trimming by flake removal, which results in decreasing the width-thickness-ratio of the blank. It is thus possible that there is a reduction sequence starting with the lateral exploitation of thick blanks which are later shortened and used as carinated cores, where bladelets are produced from the dorsal front. In most cases, the blank's ventral surface serves as striking platform and bladelets are produced from the narrow end of the blank (Fig. 5f). The length of the bladelet is determined by the thickness of the initial blank that serves as a core. In their technological and morphological characteristics, these cores-on-flakes are thus identical to so-called carinated cores, and also 'nosed' specimens occur (Fig. 6j-k). Cores-on-flakes are also used for flake production, mostly in a discoidal/centripetal way (Fig. 5g; Fig. 6l). If only the ventral face is exploited, discarded cores resemble *Kombewa* cores. If both sides are exploited, discarded cores may even resemble crudely shaped bifacial pieces.

The large differences in artefact counts of archaeological horizons AH 1 (n=40), AH 102 (n=162), and AH 2 (n=1098) obviously set a limit to the significance of quantitative comparisons. With this problem in mind, however, a brief overview may at least highlight

principal similarities and differences between the assemblages. The longest cores can be found in AH 2, whereas the widest come from AH 102 and the thickest from AH 1. In their median dimensions, flakes are roughly as long as wide in AH 102 and longer than wide in AH 2, while flakes in AH 1 are wider than long and show the highest values for median thickness (Fig. 5; Table 3 for values and number of cases). In all archaeological horizons, but most pronounced in AH 1, the median length of flakes is clearly smaller than that of blades and bladelets, while median thickness is comparable (Fig. 7). With regard to all blades and bladelets, it can be observed that the median values for all dimensions (length, width, and thickness) are consistently highest for AH 1, second highest for AH 2, and lowest for AH 102. The median values of blades and bladelets obtained along the lateral and distal edges of blanks ('burin bladelets'; Fig. 6f) are generally higher than the median values of all other blades and bladelets, with those of AH 2 and AH 102 being identical. The median width of these burin bladelets is generally smaller than that of all blades/bladelets, while the thickness is slightly larger. A comparison of the median dimensions thus suggests differences between the assemblages, with AH 2 and AH 102 clearly being more similar to one another than both are to AH 1. Within AH 2, preparation flakes are longer, thicker, but above all wider in their median value than other flakes. However, the largest median dimensions of all flakes are displayed by Kombewa flakes, which are very similar to burin bladelets in both length and thickness.

The marked numeric differences also limit the strength of the typological comparison. However, some distinction can be made (Fig. 8; Table 4). For one, backed bladelets are predominantly found in AH 1. In fact, the only other specimen, recorded from AH 2, is probably made on a burin bladelet and most of the retouch originates from a retouch which was already present prior to the detachment of the piece. Subsequently, the retouch was complemented by negatives produced from the ventral side of the piece itself to the former dorsal side. Retouched micro-bladelets (Fig. 6a-e), in contrast, are exclusive to AH 2. Laterally retouched pieces are most numerous in AH 2 and AH 102, followed by endscrapers. Thus, also with regard to typology, AH 2 and AH 102 seem to be more similar to each other than one of them is to AH 1.

In comparison to the previous excavations' inventory, the ratio among the numerous tools is similar to the one found in the lower horizons AL 2-4. With 55%, laterally retouched pieces clearly dominate over endscrapers with 22%. This is also observed for AL 1, but in a considerably lower ratio of 35% to 12%. Interestingly, the number of backed bladelets in AL 1 (n=10, 6%) is significantly higher than in all lower horizons AL 2-4 (n=9, 0.5%). Retouched

micro-bladelets are also present, but certainly underrepresented given the excavation technique applied by Brandtner (Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016).

At this stage of research, it can thus be summarised that the AH 2 and AH 102 lithics are more similar to each other than to the AH 1 assemblage from both a technological and typological perspective while no assessment is possible for AH 101 due to scarcity of artefacts (n=2). At the same time, typological similarities can be attested for AH 1 and AL 1, as well as for AH 2/102 and AL 2-4.

3.2 Lithic raw material determination and provenance

The uneven distribution of numbers in the investigated lithic assemblages from AH 1/101 and AH 2/102 (38 vs. 1213 pieces) has already been thematised above. The preliminary results presented here should thus be treated with caution. Emerging trends in raw material composition, however, allow for preliminary interpretations. Hence, the results of our raw material studies are presented accordingly. Raw material distributions for AH 2 and AH 102 confirm the results of the technological and typological assessment and show no significant differences. In agreement with the typo-technological analyses, we can therefore consider the two units in one assemblage.

A map of the lithic source areas relevant for Kammern-Grubgraben (Fig. 9) shows the three distance classes we distinguish for assessing raw material procurement: local (< 20 km), regional (20-100 km), and supra-regional (or far-distance, i.e. > 100 km). Local materials from a catchment area of fewer than 20 km include chert, radiolarite, spiculite and siliceous limestone from the Northern Calcareous Alps, as well as vein quartz and granulite from the Bohemian Massif. All these materials can be collected from gravels of the Danube River, the latter two also from gravels of the Kamp river. Materials from deposits farther away than 20 km are characterised as regional and comprise cherts from Northern Lower Austrian gravels and South Moravia, radiolarite from the St. Veit Klippen Belt, jasper from the Waldviertel/Znojmo area, and Flysch Zone quartzite. Clear quartz can be found in the Waldviertel (and overall in the Bohemian Massif). Supra-regional connections are attested for by the presence of materials derived from distances of more than 100 km, which comprise Carpathian radiolarite, erratic flint, and silicites from the Kraków-Częstochowa Upland (Moreau et al., 2016, 2017; Přichystal, 2013; Thomas et al., 2016).

For AH 1/101, raw materials from the St. Veit Klippen Zone, i.e. regional sources, and erratic flints from supra-regional procurement areas overweigh the assemblage in number (Fig. 10a; Table 5). In regard to weight distribution, however, which is more relevant for assessing

procurement strategies, the picture changes, and shows that Carpathian radiolarite dominates over erratic flint, followed by materials from regional and finally local sources. Dominance of radiolarite, although undifferentiated, in AL 1 was already observed by the previous excavators (West and Montet-White, 1990).

Numerically, the AH 2/102 assemblage is clearly dominated by erratic flint, and, to a lesser extent, local materials and Carpathian radiolarites (Fig. 10b; Table 5). Regional sources are represented in far lower quantities, and Jurassic cherts from the Kraków-Częstochowa Upland are only present in small numbers. According to weight distribution, local and regional materials outweigh erratic flint, which represents a dominating element here as well, whereas Carpathian radiolarite and Jurassic Kraków chert are only minor components. The local component also includes larger blocks of vein quartz and granulite, accounting for the dominance of this group regarding weight when compared to the number of specimens, especially in comparison to erratic flint.

3.3 Classification and provenance of adornments

In general, the new adornment inventory of 39 objects corresponds to that of the previous excavations and demonstrates a dominance of fossils. Some fossil species such as shark teeth (Fig. 11l-m), however, were not yet recovered, as well as perforated fox canines (Fig. 11h-k). This may be due to shorter time and smaller area of the new excavations. With the exception of one stone object, all newly recovered adornments are fossils (Table 6). Tubular fossilisations are most frequently represented with 32 finds, whereby dentalia (*Scaphopoda*) dominate over serpulids (*Protula*). Two dentalia show wavy to jagged circumferential defects representing lifetime repair zones of the damaged calcareous tubes. Gastropods are represented with four pieces. One gastropod shell (*Melanopsis*) was perforated by incision (Fig. 11f). The surface of a cone snail (*Plagioconus austriacoe*) (Fig. 11g) shows a flat cut with unclear function. A notched seashell (*Anadara diluvii*) fragmented either during the perforation process or at a later time (Fig. 11d). The occurrence of this perforation technique at Kammern-Grubgraben was already mentioned by Brandtner (1996). Another singular find is a longitudinally fragmented belemnite, which shows a circumferential incision (Einwögerer, 2017), indicating intentional use as pendant. A comparative object is known from the Magdalenian of the Burkhardtshöhle in Germany (Simon, 2012). A roughly shaped limestone object (Fig. 11r) shows commenced drillings from two sides aimed at producing a biconical perforation. The artefact was subsequently discarded and thus represents the

perform of a perforated stone disc, several of which have been reported from the previous excavations (Brandtner, 1990; Montet-White, 1990).

Most fossils date to the Badenian, a regional chronostratigraphic stage of the Miocene (Neogene) in the Paratethys (Wessely, 2006). One gastropod (*Melanopsis*), however, can be placed in the (later) Pannonian stage of the Miocene. Remarkably, this object was recovered from AH 1. Noticeable is also the difference between AH 2 and AH 102 whereby the latter provided only two objects, a belemnite and a cone snail, both of which thus far singular in the recent fieldwork's inventory.

The fossils originate from marine deposits of the Central Paratethys. Based on their state of preservation, an origin from secondary deposits, e.g. Danube gravels, can be excluded. Documented sources for accessible primary deposits are the Alpine-Carpathian Foredeep east of the site (Pervesler et al., 2004), and the southern Vienna Basin, farther away to the southeast (Papp et al., 1978). *Melanopsis* is the only fossil in the inventory from the Pannonian. Since the habitat for this snail was the former Lake Pannon, it most likely originates from the Vienna Basin. The belemnite, in contrast, originates from Jurassic or Cretaceous formations. Since a taxonomic classification is still pending, a specific region of origin cannot be indicated yet. Unlike the Neogene fossils, however, the belemnite could also derive from secondary deposits, e.g. the Danube.

3.4 Complexity of stone slab features

The recent excavations provided new insights not only regarding the extent (Fig. 3) but also variability and complexity of stone slab constructions. Descriptions of the first excavators observed stone middens with stones piled on each other (Montet-White 1988) but focussed more on the horizontal arrangements. These were referred to as 'pavements' and interpreted as domestic units where different activities took place (Montet-White 1990). Most completely exposed was structure Id/e, for the north part of which a habitation area with potential dwelling was proposed based on stacked stones 2-3 atop another. Brandtner (1996) claims the term 'pavement' to be misleading, and instead interprets the entire areas with horizontally lined stone slabs as dwellings for which he suggested reconstruction in form of large yurt-like structures (Brandtner and Klíma, 1995).

Our observations regarding the stone slab features document a high degree of variability and thus suggest multi-functionality of the constructions. In trench Z-D/2-3 on the lower terrace (Fig. 3 for position of trenches), horizontal arrangement of stone slabs created a flat surface, a construction that could indeed be referred to as 'pavement' (Fig. 12a). Here, we did not

document stacked stones at all. Furthermore, we documented that the structure only continues a short distance into square E3, while a drill core suggested that the structure possibly continues another ca. 3 m to the southwest, while definitely not continuing as far southeast as C12-13.

Sounding TP86 was already dug by the previous excavators, who, however, only exposed the top of the main archaeological sequence in half the area while AL 2 was not reached in the other half. We could therefore document the occurrence of stone slabs throughout the trench. Collapsed stacks of 2-3 stones occurred together with postholes, as well as large amounts of chipped stone artefacts and fragmented faunal remains. Due to a high degree of post-occupational displacement and small area of excavation, the finding indicates the former presence of stone constructions but does not allow for a conclusive interpretation. The previous excavations documented that the density of stone slabs faded out to the southwest (Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016). Excavation of trench 3, however, showed that stone features re-appear farther to the southwest (Fig. 12d). To date, we only exposed the uppermost stone slabs, but this already substantiates the presence of both, areas with horizontally aligned slabs, and collapsed stone stacks. A connection to the lower terrace is not yet entirely established but we already know that there are at least three separate concentrations of stone constructions on the site: one within the area of previous excavations, another one in trench 3 (the collapse in TP86 could represent a lateral area of the latter; drill cores showed stone slabs up to ca. 4.5 m southwest of TP86 in direction of square E3), and the surface documented in Z-D/2-3. Trench 1 provided the most complex feature. After removal of the unstructured collapse, we documented structured collapse where original position and minimum height of stone stacks and direction of fall were still determinable, as well as stacks preserved up to six stones high (Fig. 12b). Remains of 3-4 parallel walls spaced ca. 0.6 m apart are preserved and continue into the profile (Fig. 12c). Noticeably, the spacing between the walls is a little less than the length of the largest slab which was exposed in a slanted position, still partly resting on one of the walls, suggesting it may have served as cover stone (Fig. 12 b, right). Extensive traces of burning, partly connected to horizontally placed stone plates were documented only at the construction's base, and indicate plurifunctionality and/or multiphasing. The installation's northwest part must have been removed by previous excavations, and we are currently tracing it to the southeast.

As to material and provenance of the stone slabs, we can confirm the previous excavators' assessment that the raw materials range from arkose to gneiss/paragneiss and amphibolite, and

were collected from the immediate proximity i.e. outcrops and gullies of the Heiligenstein and Geißberg hills (Montet-White, 1990; Geologische Bundesanstalt, 1984).

3.5 Stratigraphy and formation

Although we can state a high degree of agreement with the observations of the previous excavations, in particular regarding the general stratigraphic frame (Haesaerts, 1990) there are a number of discordances. Starting with the latest archaeological horizon AH 1/101, it is apparent that it corresponds to AL 1. In contrast to previous excavations (Montet-White and Williams, 1994), however, the newly investigated areas did not provide indications for anything in situ. Artefacts and stone fragments occur sparsely and are mostly, but not exclusively, connected to a pronounced 5 cm thick sandy band indicating redeposition. The slope suggests origin from the northwest. An important indication of the slope processes is provided by profile TR85 and testpit TP85 (positions see Fig. 3), where AL 1 is located 1 m, resp. 1.3 m above AL 2 (Haesaerts, 1990), whereas this distance is reduced to less than 0.3 m in trench 1. This erosional unconformity has already been observed by Haesaerts (1990). Regarding AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4, our observations do not confirm that this represents a sequence of at least three separate occupations. We consider the uppermost part of this sequence, referred to as AL 2a e.g. in Haesaerts and Damblon (2016), as post-occupational collapse and displacement but do acknowledge multiple episodes in the sense of events and activities for the lower part. In particular the stone slabs have seen re-arrangements by both construction and deconstruction of features. This may be the reason why the previous excavators were not always able to separate AL 2 and AL 3, and did not agree on a reproducible definition (Montet-White, 1990; Brandtner, 1996; Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016). Hitherto unclear is the situation regarding the burning at the base of the stone construction in trench 1 which could be regarded as separate archaeological layer. Since it was excavated only in 2019, results are still pending. Not here, but in the middle of trench 3 we observed a local separation of a lower layer, unfortunately void of significant finds, by 1-2 cm of intercalated sediment. The three deep soundings we excavated so far did not provide any indication for a lower archaeological layer that may correspond to AL 5. In the AL 2-4 sequence the previous excavators documented two '5-10 cm bands of black humus' (Montet-White, 1988), denominated HH 1, corresponding to AL 4, and HH 2, connected to AL 2-3 (Haesaerts, 1990). Although we acknowledge the presence of one and in some places two dark bands, our observations and first analyses cannot confirm organic

components, neither ash nor humus, but suggest disintegration of stone slabs as source of the material, and periglacial and/or slope processes as depositional agent.

Post-occupational disturbances by palaeochannels have already been observed earlier both in testpit TP85 and in the hollow way (Haesaerts, 1990). Excavations in trench Z-D/2-3 showed that the stone slab pavement was truncated by the palaeochannel running north-northeast to south-southwest which is today cut by the hollow way. This channel corresponds to the tectonically induced drainage forming the west limit of the site (Fig. 3; see above).

3.6 Radiocarbon chronology

So far, five samples of the new excavations have been selected and dated at the Curt-Engelhorn-Zentrum Archäometrie in Mannheim (Table 7). Sample ID 753 (MAMS-26430) was collected from AH 102 on the lower terrace; sample ID 2281 (MAMS-30165) from AH 2 in TP86; ID 2812 (MAMS-32966) from AH 1 and samples ID 7759 and 7750 (MAMS-40115 and MAMS-40116) from AH 2 in trench 1. The ages fall between ca. 23 and 22 ka BP and in general agree with the chronology established previously (Haesaerts et al. 2016). The youngest age was produced for AH 102, followed by AH 1, while the ages for AH 2 are a bit earlier. Considering, however, that the two ages produced on samples from the stone installation in trench 1 already differ almost as much as the third sample from AH 2 and the one from AH 1, and that the age produced for AH 102 is younger than the age for AH 1, i.e. inverse to the stratigraphy, it appears that the potential resolution of the results should not be over-estimated. This is supported by the complex formation issues with AH 1 mentioned above. In contrast to Haesaerts et al. (2016), we choose to include all radiocarbon data in our model. Two significantly younger ages (Lv-1821 and Lv-1825), however, are plotted as single age data points only but not included in the sum plots of probability distributions (Fig. 13). This does not change the general chronological placement of the main occupation sequence as posterior to Greenland Stadial (GS-) 3.

3.7 Luminescence and dosimetry results

Luminescence investigations were carried out using the single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) protocol (Murray and Wintle, 2000; 2003). Stimulation of the luminescence signals with the blue light emitting diodes was maintained for 40 s at 125 °C, while the signals were recorded through a 7.5 mm thick Hoya U-340 UV filter. The net CW-OSL signal was evaluated from the first 0.308 s of the decay curve with an early background subtraction assessed from the 1.69-2.30 s interval (Cunningham and Wallinga, 2010). A preheat

temperature of 220 °C for 10 s and a cutheat to 180 °C were employed throughout the SAR protocol. The OSL response to a fixed test dose of 17 Gy was used through the whole set of measurements to correct for sensitivity changes. At the end of each SAR cycle a high-temperature bleach for 40 s at 280°C was performed by stimulation with the blue diodes (Murray and Wintle, 2003).

The suitability of these particular samples for De determination using the SAR protocol was tested in terms of recycling, IR depletion and recuperation tests. The aliquots with recycling and IR depletion ranging between 0.9 and 1.1 were accepted for equivalent dose estimation. Recuperation values within 0.2% of the natural signal were exhibited by all the investigated aliquots, indicating that the growth curves pass very close to the origin and that transfer of charge during the SAR protocol is negligible. The equivalent doses were determined by projecting the sensitivity corrected natural OSL signal onto the dose response curve constructed in each case. The growth of the OSL signal is best described by the sum of two saturating exponential functions. The average De values and OSL ages are presented in Table 8 along with other data relevant to optical age and uncertainty calculation. For each investigated sample, 12-22 replicate measurements of the equivalent dose were performed. The samples derive from two locations, a profile of the previous excavations (Fig. 4a), and the deep sounding in square E3 (Fig. 4b). Since, in 2015, only an assessment of the previous excavations' limits was conducted in order to determine the location where trench 1 was to be dug in subsequent years, the exposed sediment sequence was very limited. We therefore only sampled the sediment beneath the main occupation sequence AL 2-4, resp. AH 2 (ID 931 & 932). The same relative stratigraphic position (here: beneath AH 102) was also assessed in the sample sequence extracted from square E3 (ID 1482 & 1483). The four samples provide comparable ages which fall into GS-3 which is in agreement with the radiocarbon data placing the main occupation phase posterior to GS-3 (Fig. 13). Both, congruent and consistent ages are also provided by the samples from the sediment unit above AH 102 (ID 1479 & 1480), as well as the sample pair from the lowest position (ID 1485 & 1486) targeting, however, a much earlier sedimentation episode entirely unrelated to the archaeological context. In contrast, the uppermost samples extracted from above AH 101 (ID 1476 & 1477) provided incongruent ages, the earlier of which is stratigraphically inverse.

4. Discussion

The results presented support the previously assessed chronostratigraphic position of the main occupation sequence AL 2-4 resp. AH 2/102 at Kammern-Grubgraben. Although the

postulated presence of humic horizons connected to this sequence cannot be confirmed, our observations clearly support reduced aeolian input leading to increased weathering as indicated by the pronounced dark-coloured bands of sediment formed by disintegrated stone slabs, as well as wind erosion of light-weighted particles, most significant of which are potentially charcoal and other burnt vegetal remains. The high amount of burning traces and burnt sediment interfaces stands in contrast not only to absence of charcoal and ash, which we tested by flotation of the excavated sediments, but also of very low numbers of burnt and/or calcinated faunal hard tissue remains, confirmed by water-screening of the sediments. If, therefore, animal bones were not systematically used as fuel for the abundant fires, it seems justified assuming that wood or other vegetal material had indeed been used as fuel, but that the remains were blown out by the wind. The presence of more stable surfaces prone to increased weathering and erosion implies the presence of enough vegetation which would have provided both, the required fuel as well as food for the hunted ungulates (Logan, 1990). The presence of shrubs and some trees is also supported by the malacofauna (Frank and Rabeder, 1996). Vegetated surfaces obviously imply at least incipient soil formation. We therefore don't deny pedogenic processes connected to the main occupation sequence but cannot confirm the presence of humic horizons in the stratigraphic record. As already suggested by Zöller (2001) this does not rule out the presence of pedogenic micro-structures which often seem more pronounced in archaeological layers due to significantly higher concentrations of organic materials, i.e. waste. Using the Gravettian site Grub-Kranawetberg as example, Schilt et al. (2017) proposed the potential development of short-term post-occupational anthrosols for Palaeolithic campsites due to increased activity of invertebrates. Similar microstructures have also been observed for the main occupation layer at Krems-Wachtberg (Händel, 2017).

Returning to the chronostratigraphic placement (Fig. 13), it is thus most probable that the main occupation (AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4) occurred posterior to the dust peaks at the end of GS-3 and onset of sediment accumulation in the second half of GS-2.1 (Mayewski et al., 1997). Although this obviously coincides with interstadials GI-2.2 and GI-2.1, we do not agree with Haesaerts (1990) resp. Haesaerts and Damblon (2016) that the archive's sedimentary and chronological resolution allows for attributing single archaeological layers to specific interstadials. Considering the short timespans of these events of ca. 120 years each, interrupted by 200 year GS-2.2 (Rasmussen et al., 2014), it is highly unlikely that radiometric approaches can provide the required accuracy. Maximal counting errors of +/- 298-286 years (i.e. estimated definition uncertainty 1 data point/20 years) for this part of the INTIMATE

event stratigraphy add further uncertainty. In addition, it has not yet been convincingly shown that GI-2, not speaking of a distinction between GI-2.1 and GI-2.2, is well represented in regional loess sediment archives (Marković et al., 2015; Terhorst et al., 2015).

Zooming out again to the chronology model for all LGM sites in the Kamp valley area, there appears to be a considerable occupation hiatus throughout a greater part of GS-2 between Kammern-Grubgraben and the Magdalenian site Kamegg (Fig. 2), where the chronology previously determined but questioned (Verpoorte, 2004) was recently confirmed by a new ^{14}C date (Table 7), despite parallels to Kammern-Grubgraben regarding reindeer and horse-based subsistence as well as presence of horizontally aligned stone plates (Brandtner, 1954/55). With the exception of Slovakia, the apparent occupation hiatus in the Kamp area cannot, however, be reproduced for the region (e.g. Nerudová and Neruda, 2015). On this background, the significantly younger age produced for a sample from AL 1 (Lv-1825) at Kammern-Grubgraben (Fig. 13) could indicate, together with our observations regarding the formation of AH 1/101 and the occurrence of artefacts generally considered later than the age span determined for the main occupation sequence, most significant of which is a bâton percé recovered from the surrounding of a hearth in AL 1 (Neugebauer-Maresch et al., 2016), the presence of a later component in AH 1/101 resp. AL 1. The co-occurrence of radiocarbon ages and material congruent with the main occupation sequence AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4, can be resolved by interpreting AH 1/101 resp. AL 1 as palimpsest of different occupations which is supported by the observation of slope processes (3.5) representing a major factor for sediment accumulation in the area (Händel et al., 2009), as well as the new luminescence data which provides incongruent ages for the sediment above (3.7). This interpretation would also account for the presence of backed bladelets, the systematic production of which does not agree with the general characteristics of the AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4 industry (3.1).

The lithic inventory of this main archaeological unit is not unique with regard to its technological and typological characteristics, but finds both regional and supra-regional equivalents. Regional similarities exist to assemblages from sites such as Kašov I in Slovakia (Bánész et al., 1992) or Stránská skála IV in Moravia (Svoboda and Novák, 2004). Other comparable regional assemblages are reported from Rosenberg in Lower Austria (Ott, 1996) or Mohelno-Plevovce in Moravia (Škrdla, 2016). Overall technological and typological similarities of these with assemblages from eastern Europe, such as Anetovka I or Muralovka, have been pointed out using the umbrella-term of the so-called 'Epi-Aurignacian industry with Sagaidak-Muralovka-type microliths (EASMM)' (Demidenko et al., 2019). Within the so-termed assemblages, flake production from discoidal cores is important and occurs

alongside the production of blades, bladelets and micro-bladelets from unidirectional volumetric cores, carinated cores-on-flake and from the distal and lateral edges of blanks. With regard to the typological spectrum, laterally retouched micro-bladelets are characteristic. There are thus discernable parallels between the technological and typological characteristics documented for the artefacts from AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4 and the EASMM assemblages. The presence of fine borers, raclette-like artefacts (Fig. 6g-i), and pieces with heavy lateral retouch, however, sets the inventory of Kammern-Grubgraben a bit apart from Mohelno-Plevovce and Rosenberg (and other EASMM assemblages), but underlines similarities to the (Late) Badegoulian assemblages in France, such as Le Cuzoul de Vers and Lassac (Ducasse, 2010), otherwise also very similar with regard to technological characteristics. Ságvár in Hungary also shows comparable technological and typological characteristics (Lengyel, 2018), but the notable presence of backed bladelets sets it closer to AH 1/101 resp. AL 1. Chronologically, Cuzoul de Vers (layers 22-31) and AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4 seem to be roughly contemporaneous. A single date with a large standard deviation places the occupation at Rosenberg around 24 ka (Fig. 2; Table 7). Eventually, it can be stated that the Kammern-Grubgraben AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4 inventory exhibits strong similarities to both Mohelno-Plevovce and Rosenberg (and other assemblages attributed to the EASMM) as well as to assemblages of the French Badegoulian (Montet-White, 1994; Terberger and Street, 2002).

In addition to lithic technology and typology, Kammern-Grubgraben and some of the EASMM sites also have the occurrence of stone slab constructions in common. Stone features have been documented at Mohelno-Plevovce (Škrdla et al., 2018) and Muralovka (Demidenko et al., 2019), as well as, although not as convincing at Rosenberg (Ott, 1996). Another roughly contemporaneous site in the region with similar features is Stránska skála IV (Svoboda and Novák, 2004). At all these sites, however, the stone constructions lack the diversity and complexity we observe for Kammern-Grubgraben (3.4), and interpretations focus on regarding them as planar features in the sense of pavements creating dry living spaces and/or dwellings (e.g. Škrdla et al., 2016; Demidenko et al., 2019). While the horizontally placed stone slabs in trench Z-D/2-3 (Fig. 12a) support a similar interpretation, the stone features documented in the other trenches, in particular trench 1, demonstrate that the features encompass rising constructions, i.e. parallel narrow walls one stone wide and up to six stones high (Fig. 12b,c). As investigations are still ongoing, we are far from being able to present a conclusive interpretation. We can, however, state that the construction at least in trench 1 is clearly multiphased and most probably plurifunctional, based on the observation of

various intense but unconnected burning traces at the base but not in the upper part of the feature. This suggests that the stones have been rearranged to serve different purposes, the earlier of which are obviously connected to combustion. The 'final' construction with the parallel walls, however, is more difficult to interpret. Based on ethnographic sources, Einwögerer (2017) suggested a meat cache, but other types of storage facilities, installations for smoking meat or other products, or something entirely different should be regarded as equally possible at this point of research. Also not yet clear at present is the temporal/functional connection of the rising constructions to the underlying layer with burning traces and fragmented animal bones. Extension of trench 1 will hopefully provide a more robust basis for reconstruction and reading. To be considered for interpretation on the level of an entire camp is also the extensive evidence for intact and collapsed stacks of 2-3 stones documented in trenches 3 and TP86. These are by no means unique to the recent excavations but were already documented in a greater part of the previous excavations' profile documentation, drawings, and photographs (Brandtner, 1996; Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016; Montet-White, 1990), where the many stacked stones suggest a considerable portion of rising stone constructions. This stands in contrast to main line of interpretation of the previous excavators who focussed on the horizontal extent of the stone features narrowing the potential interpretation to a stratigraphic sequence of stone slab pavements interpreted as dwellings, equated with occupations. In analogy, it should be considered that the stone constructions documented at the contemporaneous sites mentioned above may also possibly include elements of higher complexity, which have been obliterated by post-occupational processes. Lithic technology and typology, and more so the stone slab constructions, demonstrate the transport of ideas within a network of contemporaneous sites. In addition, however, also the transport of materials is accounted for by raw material provenance studies. Regarding the recent investigations at Kammern-Grubgraben, this has, so far, been conducted for lithic raw materials and fossil molluscs.

Preliminary microscopic analyses on the lithic raw materials reveal specific procurement patterns. Since numeric comparisons between the materials from AH 1/101 and AH 2/102 can be misleading, we focused on weight distribution in relation to the distance of the identified source regions (e.g. Newman, 1994). As for AH 1/101, we observe a dominance of extra-local materials, mainly represented by Carpathian radiolarites and erratic flint. In contrast, AH 2/102 is characterised by a wider variety of materials, including cherts from the Kraków-Częstochowa Upland, which are absent in the AH 1/101 assemblage. In direct comparison, local materials appear to be over-dominant in AH 2/102 due to individual larger artefacts

made of quartz and granulite, while regional materials as well as erratic flint seem to be similarly distributed within the assemblages. The most noticeable difference between the two archaeological horizons concerns the weight proportions of the Carpathian radiolarites, which clearly overweigh all other raw material types in AH 1/101. Hence, it seems that we are able to grasp elements of a highly specialised procurement strategy focused on radiolarite in AH 1/101, an observation which is supported by the exclusive presence of St. Veit Klippen Belt radiolarites from the regional supply zone next to far-distance Carpathian radiolarites (compare Féblot-Augustins, 2009; Kuhn, 1992). The general lithic raw material distribution patterns thus exhibit strong tendencies towards the northeast which has already been suggested by Pawlikowski (1990), and support embedding the site in central and eastern European Epigravettian contexts (e.g. Demidenko et al., 2018; Rios-Garaizar et al., 2019). In few cases, potential contemporaneous primary workshops are documented from source areas, such as Kraków Spadzista layer 5 for cherts from the Kraków-Częstochowa Upland (Wilczyński, 2015). Tendencies in lithic raw material procurement to the northeast also appear to be in accordance to subsistence strategies regarding reindeer in particular, for which seasonal (summer) migrations through the Moravian gate have been postulated (West, 1997). For the faunal remains of AL 2-4, studied in the course of previous investigations, this would agree with the seasonality data pointing to winter (Logan, 1990).

The pattern is less precisely defined with regard to the procurement of fossil molluscs used as adornments (Table 6), most of which originate from Badenian deposits (except for the AH 1 specimen from the Pannonian). The closest sources for these fossils are marine deposits of the Alpine-Carpathian Foredeep (Pervesler et al., 2004). Well-known modern fossil-bearing exposures are located in the Grund formation ca. 30 km northeast of Kammern-Grubgraben (Harzhauser and Landau 2016; Roetzel 2009). Other well-known exposures, inter alia the stratotype profile (Papp et al., 1978), are located around Baden in the Vienna Basin ca. 65 km southeast of the site. Although neither far-distance transport from sources farther away nor local procurement from hitherto undocumented locations can be excluded, we choose considering closest known sources more likely and thus consider the underlying procurement system as regional. Since deposits of Lake Pannon also occur in the Vienna Basin, no evident geographic differentiation can be made between AH 1 and AH 2. The noticeable difference between the very small assemblage from AH 102, which provided one belemnite and a cone shell but no dentalia, and AH 2 can, at this stage, be best explained by functional intra-site differences between the stone slab pavement area in trench Z-D/2-3, and the more complex stone structures in the trenches on the upper terrace.

In a final point of this discussion we would like to turn to adaptation to the unfavourable environmental conditions during the LGM, particularly in winter. In the material culture, this is not so much demonstrated by the lithic industry or the adornments, but rather by artefacts reflecting more fundamental technological innovation. In this context, Kammern-Grubgraben provided substantial evidence for the regular use of eyed needles produced on animal bone splinters (Fig. 11q). This artefact category not only reflects supra-regional contact and distribution patterns for innovations (Terberger, 2013) but is fundamentally crucial for the production of fine seams essential for the manufacture of wind- and water-repellent clothing (Osborn, 2014; Pitulko and Pavlova, 2019).

5. Conclusions

New research at Kammern-Grubgraben, so far, confirmed a number of results gained by previous investigations, but also produced a range of novel insights. Whereas the previous chronological assessment was in general confirmed, the new luminescence ages produced on samples recovered from two different positions bracketing in situ preserved archaeological structures of the main archaeological sequence AH 2/102 resp. AL 2-4 now allow for its more robust chronostratigraphic placement between the GS-3 dust peaks and onset of GS-2.1 sedimentation. Although this comprehends a connection of the main occupation sequence to GI-2 (GI-2.2/GI-2.1) or shortly thereafter, data resolution and absence of humic horizons does not allow for more precise placement. In a similar sense, eyed needles as well as technology and typology of the chipped stone industry demonstrate extensive supra-regional contacts on a rather coarse temporal scale.

A high degree of mobility of the hunter-gatherer groups is demonstrated by the raw material economy. The lithic raw material composition of both assemblages, attest for strong relationships towards the northeast. This is evidenced by the dominance of supra-local raw materials originating from sources more than 100 km away from the site. The fossils used for adornments, in contrast, indicate connections on a regional scale to the east and southeast. Despite some differences between AH 1/101 and AH 2/102 in material culture and procurement strategy, the general mobility pattern appears persistent.

Of high significance is the determination of considerably greater extent of not only the archaeological layers but also of settlement structures with stone slab features. In combination with the recent assessment that these features represent constructions of higher complexity than hitherto assumed, this suggests not only rethinking the functionality of these structures but also site function as a whole.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the financial support for fieldwork which has been provided by the Federal State of Lower Austria and the Federal Monuments Authority Austria (Bundesdenkmalamt). For the luminescence investigations we acknowledge the financial support of the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program ERC-2015-STG (Grant Agreement No. 678106) during the research stage at the Nordic Laboratory for Luminescence Dating, Roskilde, Denmark. S.M Groza-Săcaciuc gratefully acknowledges the help of Jan-Pieter Buylaert for providing the analytical facilities for luminescence analyses. We are grateful for the species identification of the fossil molluscs used for adornments carried out by Andreas Kroh and, for *Plagioconus austriacoe* (Sacco, 1893), by Mathias Harzhauser (Department of Geology and Palaeontology, Natural History Museum Vienna). Furthermore we thank Reinhard Roetzel (Geological Survey of Austria GBA) for numerous remarks on the provenance of the fossils. Irene Petschko (DIGital Documentation Lab, OREA) prepared the map of lithic source areas (Fig. 9). Roswitha Thomas (OREA) produced the photographs for Fig. 6a-e, and Nicole Bößl (Institute for Prehistoric Archaeology, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg) prepared the lithic tools plate (Fig. 6).

Tables

	AH 1	% AH	% total	AH 101	% AH	% total	AH 2	% AH	% total	AH 102	% AH	% total	no context	% AH	% total	total
total	40		3,0	2		0,2	1098		83,6	162		12,3	11		0,8	1313
cores	4	10	2,6			0,0	133	12,1	86,9	15	9,3	9,8	1	9,1	0,7	153
blades/bladelets	16	40	7,7			0,0	176	16,0	85,0	14	8,6	6,8	1	9,1	0,5	207
burin bladelets	6	15	7,2			0,0	68	6,2	81,9	8	4,9	9,6	1	9,1	1,2	83
flakes	12	30	2,0	2	100	0,3	480	43,7	80,4	97	59,9	16,2	6	54,5	1,0	597
preparation/decortification flake	1	2,5	0,5			0,0	168	15,3	88,0	20	12,3	10,5	2	18,2	1,0	191
Kombewa flake						0,0	16	1,5	94,1	1	0,6	5,9				17
crested blade						0,0	9	0,8	90,0	1	0,6	10,0				10
crested flake						0,0	10	0,9	90,9	1	25,0	9,1				11
core table						0,0	2	0,2	100,0							2
chunk	1	2,5	3,8			0,0	21	1,9	80,8	4	2,5	15,4				26
Siret						0,0	15	1,4	93,8	1	0,6	6,3				16

Table 1: Kammern-Grubgraben 2015-18: Overview of the composition of the lithic assemblages.

Core concept	AH 1			AH 2			AH 102		
	s	m	t	s	m	t	s	m	t
Opportunistic flaking concept				18	2	20	1		1
Preparation-intensive flaking concept					1	1		1	1
Kombewa concept				4	5	9			
Blade concept, "classic"				2	1	3		1	1
Blade/bladelet production from lateral and distal edges	3		3	81	9	90	6	1	7
Carinated core concept				6		6	5		5
discoidal/centripetal		1	1	1	1	2			
fracturation of blank by direct blow				7	3	10			
d'Orville/de Bertonne-like		1	1	1	2	3	1	1	2
bladelet production from dorsal ridges				1		1			

Table 2: Kammern-Grubgraben lithics 2015-18: Overview of the observed core concepts

	AH 1		AH 2		AH 102	
	n	mm	n	mm	n	mm
flakes median length	2	11,9	205	15,6	53	11,9
flakes median width	7	15,7	331	14,2	72	11,3
flakes median thickness	7	4,1	331	3,4	72	2,7
preparation flakes median length			126	17,0	15	13,2
preparation flakes median width			147	18,1	19	17,9
preparation flakes median thickness			147	4,9	19	3,8
Kombewa flakes median length			12	21,5		
Kombewa flakes median width			13	19,1		
Kombewa flakes median thickness			13	5,6		
blades/bladelets median length	2	25,5	60	19,2	1	16,2
blades/bladelets median width	11	11,8	154	10,2	13	9,0
blades/bladelets median thickness	11	4,9	154	3,3	13	3,0
burin bladelets median length	5	31,2	32	21,6	4	21,6
burin bladelets median width	6	6,8	64	7,7	8	6,6
burin bladelets median thickness	6	5,0	64	5,5	8	4,5

Table 3: Kammern-Grubgraben lithics 2015-18: Number of cases (n) and median dimensions in mm of blanks

FUNCTIONAL PARTS	AH 1	% AH	% total	AH 2	% AH	% total	AH 102	% AH	% total	total
total functional part	10		10	80		80,0	10		10	100
Laterally retouched pieces	4	40	4	33	41,3	33,0	6	60	6	43
end-scraper				18	22,5	18,0	3	30	3	21
retouche micro-bladetes				12	15,0	12,0				12
truncations				11	13,8	11,0	1	10	1	12
pointed blade				3	3,8	3,0				3
backed bladelet	4	40	4	1	1,3	1,0				5
borer	1	10	1	1	1,3	1,0				2
micro backed point				1	1,3	1,0				1
notched pices	1	10	1							1

Table 4: Kammern-Grubgraben 2015-18: Overview of lithic tools (counted in functional parts) in the lithic assemblages.

distance classification	raw material	provenance	source area in Fig. 9	n		weight	
				AH 1/101	AH 2/102	AH 1/101	AH 2/102
local (<20 km)	chert	north alpine	DRG; DW	0	31	0	96,05
	radiolarite			2	38	1,17	106,83
	spiculite			0	1	0	2,23
	silicified limestone			1	22	6,92	520,76
	vein quartz	presumably Bohemian Massif		0	63	0	889,68
	granulite			1	15	12,1	812,45
regional (20-100 km)	chert	Northern Lower Austrian gravels	NAG	0	8	0	58,95
	chert	South Moravia	SM	0	22	0	261,75
	radiolarite	St. Veit Klippen Belt	SVB	13	33	25,09	151,02
	jasper	presumably Waldviertel/ Bohemian Massif	WVZ	0	4	0	132,49
	quartzite			0	9	0	238,08
	clear quartz			0	1	0	0,32
far distance (>100 km)	chert	Kraków area	KCU	0	15	0	57,65
	radiolarite	presumably Carpathian	PKB	8	110	56,18	240,85
	erratic flint	S. Poland / N. Bohemia	EFB	13	841	36,8	1809,01

Table 5: Kammern-Grubgraben 2015-18: Lithic raw material varieties and their provenance according to number (n) and weight

Find object	Palaeontological determination	Chronostratigraphy	AH 1	AH 2	AH 102	n	%
Dentalia	Scaphopoda, sp. 1	Badenian	1	23		24	63.2
	Scaphopoda, sp. 2	Badenian		1		1	2.6
	indet.		1	2		3	8.0
Serpulids	<i>Protula</i> sp.	Badenian		3		3	8.0
	<i>Protula?</i>	Badenian		1		1	2.6
Gastropods	<i>Plagioconus austriacconoe</i> (Sacco, 1893)	Badenian			1	1	2.6
	<i>Melanopsis</i> sp.	Pannonian	1			1	2.6
	Naticidae indet.	Badenian?		1		1	2.6
	<i>Semicassis</i> sp.	Badenian		1		1	2.6
Belemnite	indet.	Jurassic or Cretaceous			1	1	2.6
Bivalve	<i>Anadara diluvia</i> (Lamarck, 1805)	Badenian		1		1	2.6
total			3	33	2	38	100

Table 6: Kammern-Grubgraben 2015-19: Fossils among the personal adornments. Palaeontological determination: Natural History Museum Vienna. Scaphopoda, sp.1 and sp.2 reference separate species without precise species identification.

Site	Labnumber	14C age BP	± (1σ)	Material	Species	ID/area	Layer	cal BP	± (1σ)	Reference
Kammern-Grubgraben	<i>Lv-1825</i>	<i>16800</i>	<i>280</i>	bone		centre	AL 1	<i>20280</i>	<i>343</i>	Gilot, 1997
Kammern-Grubgraben	GrN-21902	18380	130	bone	horse/reindeer	south	KS 1	22254	161	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-32966	18590	60	tooth	reindeer	ID 2812	AH 1	22451	64	<i>this paper</i>
Kammern-Grubgraben	<i>Lv-1821</i>	<i>17350</i>	<i>190</i>	bone	horse + reindeer	centre	AL 2b	<i>20939</i>	<i>265</i>	Gilot, 1997
Kammern-Grubgraben	Lv-1822	18620	220	bone	horse + reindeer	centre	AL 2b	22525	252	Gilot, 1997
Kammern-Grubgraben	Lv-1823	18070	270	bone	horse + reindeer	centre	AL 2a	21921	340	Gilot, 1997
Kammern-Grubgraben	GrN-21529	18890	180	bone	horse/reindeer	south	KS 2	22741	207	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-25868	19320	60	tooth	reindeer	I/G/East	AL 2	23267	139	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-25869	19330	70	tooth	reindeer	I/G/East	AL 2	23278	146	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-26430	18300	70	bone	horse/reindeer	ID 753	AH 102	22185	130	<i>this paper</i>
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-30165	19250	70	bone	horse/reindeer	ID 2281	AH 2	23188	144	<i>this paper</i>
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-40115	18860	60	bone	horse/reindeer	ID 7759	AH 2	22708	118	<i>this paper</i>
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-40116	19230	60	bone	horse/reindeer	ID 7950	AH 2	23163	139	<i>this paper</i>
Kammern-Grubgraben	Lv-1660	18170	300	bone	horse + reindeer	TR 85	AL 3-4	22031	347	Haesaerts, 1990
Kammern-Grubgraben	Lv-1810	18030	270	bone	horse + reindeer	centre	AL 3	21870	349	Gilot, 1997
Kammern-Grubgraben	GrN-21530	18920	90	bone	horse/reindeer	south	KS 3	22775	140	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-25870	19170	60	tooth	reindeer	III/G/West	AL 3	23078	134	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-25871	19070	70	tooth	reindeer	III/G/West	AL 3	22960	125	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	AA-1746	18960	290	bone		TR 85	AL 4?	22828	333	Haesaerts, 1990
Kammern-Grubgraben	Lv-1680	18400	330	bone		C/D	AL 4	22222	370	Haesaerts, 1990
Kammern-Grubgraben	GrN-21531	19380	90	bone	horse/reindeer	south	KS 4	23337	161	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	GrN-21790	19270	80	bone	horse (inner part)	N trench HH1	AL 4	23212	151	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	GrN-21893	18820	160	bone	horse (outer part)	N trench HH1	AL 4	22678	179	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-25872	19290	70	tooth	reindeer	III/G/East	AL 4	23234	144	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kammern-Grubgraben	MAMS-25873	19210	70	tooth	reindeer	III/G/East	AL 4	23139	145	Haesarts et al., 2016
Kamegg	GrN-22883	13840	120	bone				16761	205	Verpoorte, 2004
Kamegg	GrN-23182	14130	110	bone				17206	175	Verpoorte, 2004
Kamegg	MAMS-40114	13840	50	charcoal		ID 32		16761	130	<i>this paper</i>
Langmannersdorf A	GrN-6585	19340	100	calcinated bone				23289	166	Verpoorte, 2004
Langmannersdorf A	GrN-6586	19520	120	calcinated bone				23526	184	Verpoorte, 2004
Langmannersdorf A	GrN-6659	20580	170	calcinated bone				24782	262	Hahn, 1977
Langmannersdorf A	GrN-6660	20260	200	calcinated bone				24325	271	Hahn, 1977
Langmannersdorf A	GrA-16567	20590	110	bone	reindeer			24782	209	Verpoorte, 2004
Grossweikersdorf III	Lv-1755	20300	360	bone				24484	467	Street and Terberger, 2000
Rosenburg	Lv-1756	20120	480	bone				24275	610	Ott, 1996
Saladorf	VERA-3072	18350	80	tooth	horse		AC-AD 15-16	22247	127	Einwögerer and Simon, 2005
Saladorf	VERA-3244	17880	75	humic acids			hearth C	21679	124	Einwögerer and Simon, 2005

Table 7: Radiocarbon data of Kammern-Grubgraben and other LGM sites in Austria. Calibration with IntCal13 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2014) using OxCal 4.3 web tool - web interface build number: 122; last updated: 12/3/2020; accessed 25/3/2020 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009). Lab numbers/ages in italics are not considered for sum plots in Fig. 13.

Sample code	Depth (m)	Grain size (μm)	Water content (%)	D_e (Gy)	U-Ra (Bq/kg)	Th (Bq/kg)	K (Bq/kg)	Total random error (%)	Total systematic error (%)	Total dose rate (Gy/ka)	Age (ka)
931	1.087	63-90	10	78.2 ± 4.0 (n=11)	41.2 ± 1.1	68.3 ± 2.0	361 ± 10	5.3	6.0	2.984 ± 0.046	26.2 ± 2.1
932	1.192	63-90	10	58.4 ± 2.2 (n=8)	36.5 ± 0.4	34.8 ± 0.5	345 ± 11	4.0	6.1	2.307 ± 0.033	25.3 ± 1.9
1476	1.927	63-90	15	61.0 ± 2.2 (n=16)	40.1 ± 1.3	42.8 ± 0.8	318 ± 11	3.9	6.9	2.276 ± 0.036	26.8 ± 2.1
1477	1.927	63-90	15	53.2 ± 2.2 (n=17)	46.7 ± 2.4	49.8 ± 1.3	390 ± 10	4.5	7	2.694 ± 0.047	19.8 ± 1.6
1479	2.168	63-90	15	53.8 ± 1.8 (n=19)	53.5 ± 1.4	43.5 ± 1.6	408 ± 17	3.9	7	2.759 ± 0.055	19.5 ± 1.6
1480	2.168	63-90	15	54.1 ± 2.2 (n=19)	49.7 ± 1.1	39.2 ± 1.4	361 ± 10	4.3	7	2.500 ± 0.038	21.6 ± 1.8
1482	2.59	63-90	15	66.2 ± 2.0 (n=21)	45.1 ± 1.2	48.5 ± 0.5	372 ± 10	3.3	7	2.583 ± 0.032	25.6 ± 2.0
1483	2.59	63-90	15	66.5 ± 2.0 (n=21)	44.5 ± 0.9	47.6 ± 1.2	389 ± 10	3.3	7	2.606 ± 0.035	25.5 ± 2.0
1485	4.023	63-90	15	181.7 ± 5.1 (n=17)	43.8 ± 0.8	54.8 ± 2.1	458 ± 14	3.3	7.1	2.880 ± 0.050	63.1 ± 4.9
1486	4.023	63-90	15	233.0 ± 9.1 (n=20)	44.0 ± 0.8	47.2 ± 0.9	421 ± 10	4.1	7.1	2.666 ± 0.033	87.4 ± 7.1

Table 8: Summary of the luminescence and dosimetry data. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. All uncertainties represent 1σ . Uncertainties on the ages were calculated based on the error assessment system described by Aitken and Alldred (1972) and Aitken (1976). Specific activities were measured on well detector and the ages were determined considering a water content of 10% (due to less sediment cover for samples ID 931 and 932) and 15%, with a relative error of 25%; n denotes the number of accepted aliquots; beta attenuation and etching factor used for 63-90 μm fractions is 0.94 ± 0.05 . The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the beta and gamma radiations as well as the contribution from the cosmic radiation.

Figure captions:

Fig. 1: Location and geomorphological setting of Kammern-Grubgraben. a. Map with LGM sites in east Austria: 1 Kammern-Grubgraben, 2 Rosenberg, 3 Langmannersdorf, 4 Saladorf, 5 Großweikersdorf, 6 Kamegg (post-LGM). Map source: http://www.d-maps.com/carte.php?num_car=33844&lang=en (modified) b. Aerial view of Kammern-Grubgraben (marked by oval) from the southwest. Photograph: OREA/Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Fig. 2: Chronology model of LGM sites in the Kamp valley and adjacent areas (see Fig. 1). Radiocarbon data is presented in Table 7. Graph produced with CalPal-Beyond the Ghost, Version 2016.2, <http://www.calpal-online.de/> (Weninger & Jöris 2008; Weninger et al., 2014) showing sum plots of probability distributions of calibrated ^{14}C dates based on IntCal13 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2014) using OxCal 4.3 web tool, web interface build number: 122; last updated: 12/3/2020; accessed 25/3/2020 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009). Calibrated ages are grouped by site. All uncertainties represent 1σ . GICC05 timescale (Greenland Ice Core Chronology 2005, 15 - 42 ka; 20 yr δ 18O, <http://www.iceandclimate.nbi.ku.dk>; Andersen et al., 2006) and GISP2 Ca (GISP2 Ca Glaciochemical Data 0-70 ka calBP; Mayewski et al., 1997) plotted as implemented in CalPal-Beyond the Ghost. INTIMATE event stratigraphy refers Rasmussen et al. (2014).

Fig. 3: Kammern-Grubgraben - plan of previous and new excavations. Profile TR85, test trenches TP85 and TP86, the north trench around TP85, and the large area in the centre were assessed by previous excavations (Haesaerts and Damblon, 2016). For the large area, however, we report discrepancy between claimed and confirmed (dotted line) excavation boundaries. Trenches 1-3, TP86 (reopened), Z-D/2-3, E3, and C12-13 excavated in course of recent fieldwork.

Fig. 4: Luminescence sampling locations. a. Profile of previous excavation area (\cong northwest boundary of trench 1). b. Ortho-rectified photo of square E3's east profile. See Fig. 3 for locations on plan. Photographs: OREA/Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Fig. 5: Schematic representation of different cores-on-flakes. a. bladelet production from lateral edges; b. bladelet production from distal edge; c. bladelet production from distal edge and ventral side; d. bladelet production along dorsal ridges; e. flake production from flanks of thick, triangular blanks; f. bladelets production from distal volume of thick blanks; g. centripetal/discoidal flake production from ventral and/or dorsal face of larger flakes.

Fig. 6: Lithic tools. a-e retouched micro-bladelets; f. bladelet knapped from retouched scraper edge; g-i raclette-like tools; j carinated micro-bladelets core on endscraper with additional bladelet removal from the ventral surface; k-l core-on-flake in Kombewa-like technique; m retoucher. Photographs: OREA/Austrian Academy of Sciences; f-i A. Maier.

Fig. 7: Blank dimensions in AH 1, AH 2, and AH 102.

Fig. 8: Typological composition of the assemblages in AH 1, AH 2, and AH 102.

Fig. 9: Map of lithic source areas relevant for Kammern-Grubgraben (no. 1 in the map). DRG: Danube River gravels; DW: Dunkelsteinerwald; WVZ: Waldviertel/Znojmo area; SVB: St. Veit Klippen Belt; FZ: Flysch Zone; NAG: Northern Lower Austrian gravels; SM: South Moravia; PKB: Pieniny Klippen Belt; EFB: Erratic flint belt; KCU: Kraków-Częstochowa Upland. Map source: OREA/Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Fig. 10: Weight distributions of raw materials according to distance in AH 1/101 and AH 2/102.

Fig. 11: Personal adornments and eyed needle. a-e perforated fossil bivalve shells; f perforated fossil gastropod shell; g incised fossil gastropod shell; h-k perforated fox teeth; l-m fossil shark teeth; n-p fossil dentalia resp. serpulids; q eyed bone needle; r stone object with drilling. a-c, l-m: excavations Montet-White/Brandtner 1985-1990; e, h-k, n-p: excavations Brandtner/Klíma 1993-1994; d, f-g, q-r: excavations OREA 2005-2019. Photographs: OREA/Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Fig. 12: Stone installations at Kammern-Grubgraben. a surface made with stone slabs in trench Z-D/2-3; b partly collapsed rising stone structures in trench 1; c regularly spaced stone walls in the profile after excavation of partly collapsed stone installation in trench 1 (Fig. 12b); d exposed stone features in southwest part of trench 3. See Fig. 3 for location of trenches on plan. Photographs: OREA/Austrian Academy of Sciences.

Fig. 13: Chronostratigraphic model of archaeological contexts/occupations at Kammern-Grubgraben with ^{14}C and luminescence ages. Radiocarbon data is presented in Table 7; luminescence data in Table 8. Graph produced with CalPal-Beyond the Ghost, Version 2016.2, <http://www.calpal-online.de/> (Weninger & Jöris 2008; Weninger et al., 2014) showing sum plots of probability distributions of calibrated ^{14}C dates based on IntCal13 calibration curve (Reimer et al., 2014) using OxCal 4.3 web tool, web interface build number: 122; last updated: 12/3/2020; accessed 25/3/2020 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009). Calibrated ^{14}C ages are grouped by assigned archaeological layers. OSL ages are plotted as average values for neighbouring sample doublets (can be considered coeval as they are in agreement within error limits, see Table 8). Average values determined by applying formula B.23 of Aitken (1985; Appendix B): ID 1479 & 1480: 20.4 ± 1.5 ka; ID 1482 & 1483: 25.5 ± 1.9 ka; ID 931 & 932: 25.7 ± 1.8 ka. All uncertainties represent 1σ . GICC05 timescale (Greenland Ice Core Chronology 2005, 15 - 42 ka; 20 yr δ 18O, <http://www.iceandclimate.nbi.ku.dk>; Andersen et al., 2006) and GISP2 Ca (GISP2 Ca Glaciochemical Data 0-70 ka calBP; Mayewski et al., 1997) plotted as implemented in CalPal-Beyond the Ghost. INTIMATE event stratigraphy refers Rasmussen et al. (2014) and time of maximum volume of Alpine glaciation is given according to Seguinot et al. (2018; Fig. 4b) together with timespan with modelled total ice volume > 0.2 m s.l.e. (metres of sea level equivalent) in MIS2.

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Figure 7 online

Figure 8 online

Figure 10 online

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